

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 4.3 Documentation on the INFRA service and its functionalities

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TABLE OF CONTENT

Executive Summary	p. 4
List of Abbreviations	p. 6
1. Introduction	p. 7
2. Principles and fundamental concepts at the basis of INFRA pilot service	p. 9
3. Co-design e Co-development	p.11
4. Lessons from stakeholders for INFRA development	p.13
5. Development and implementation of INFRA	p.17
5.1. Information layers	p.17
5.2. The pilot service INFRA	p.18
5.2.1. INFRA-AEGIS	p.20
5.2.2. INFRA-SENTRY	p.21
5.3 Operating INFRA through a Cloud structure	p.24
6. Operational use of INFRA using core platforms	p.27
7. Conclusion and next steps	p.28
8. References	p.29
Appendix I - Information from users for INFRA-SENTRY	p.31

Executive Summary

The key motivation behind the project Arctic PASSION is to contribute to the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. It aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving, and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge. It also aims at streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services, and contribute to ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system.

In this report the development of an Arctic PASSION (Pilot) Service for wildfires, INFRA (INtegrated Fire Risk mAnagement), and its functionalities are presented. INFRA aims to incorporate data from observation networks and services, integrate them into a central system and transform them into useful information that can be disseminated to end-users, such as indigenous communities and organizations, and municipalities. The main purpose of this data system is to deliver an information product that benefits the end user.

The Integrated Wildfire Management (IFM) cycle consists of several interlinked and often overlapping phases:

- Risk reduction, prevention, readiness;
- Current risk evaluation;
- Wildfire detection;
- Response to fire events, and, at the end, damage assessment and recovery.

The INFRA service aims to compact and simplify access to relevant information/products which stem from diverse sources. Most importantly, it makes it possible to manage, integrate, select and transform such sets of information into a tailored product that is useful for the respective users. In this way, INFRA can contribute to GEO goals and priorities (Management and Disaster Risk Reduction) in the Arctic, supporting the whole management chain: from prevention of forest fires to management of shutdown operations, post-event management, and damage assessment. Modularity helps to tailor the service to the user's needs.

The INFRA service is based on several modules and IT platforms, the most important being:

- 1 – INFRA-AEGIS – A web-GIS platform through which it is possible to present, combine and integrate all the informational layers produced by INFRA, or collected from many other sources and services.
- 2 – INFRA-SENTRY - A platform through which to distribute information and messages to users that can be easily adapted to specific needs.

Implementing these platforms through the cloud makes them highly flexible. Using them does not demand very advanced hardware/software resources, making them more accessible to users.

The novelty of the INFRA service lies (i) in the attention to the local scale, and (ii) in having developed tools suitable for generating messages that are tailored to the category of users that are the intended target.

Interaction with users and the adaptation of products and functions to their needs are fundamental elements of INFRA. From the very beginning, dialog with various stakeholders contributed greatly in shaping the core concepts and aims of INFRA. This ongoing interaction has significantly influenced its development and the implementation of current functionalities. Notably, it has highlighted the importance of focusing on the local scale and simplifying the information thereby enabling more communities and municipalities to transfer tailored information to the end users. Adapting INFRA

to the specific needs of different users requires constant development. Through specific surveys/interviews, and by spreading information on the service and working to make it available for the 2024 fire season, we will:

- Assess the relevance of the different information layers for different users and user categories and identify needs for additional layers (i.e. about fire effects on air quality at small spatial scales);
- Collect supplementary information from users/communities (i.e. critical/relevant infrastructures, ground-based early detection systems);
- Interact with wildfire management organizations at community/local/regional level;
- Assess the relevance/value of fire effects and damages;
- Identify communities and/or other users to help test the service;
- Adapt and develop INFRA functionalities and products accordingly.

List of Abbreviations

AEGIS	Automatic GIS Environment (IT Platform)
AINA	Arctic Institute of North America
ASSW	Arctic Science Summit Week
BOLAM	Bologna Limited Area Model
CAP	Common Alerting Protocol
CWFIS	Canadian Wildland Fire Information System
EFFIS	European Forest Fire Information System
EPRR	Emergency Prevention, Preparedness and Response Working Group of Arctic Council
FBP	Forest Fire Behavior Prediction System
FIDESYS	Fire Detection System (IT Platform)
FWI	Fire Weather Index
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GWIS	Global Wildfire Information System
IFM	Integrated Fire Management System
MOLOCH	non-hydrostatic, convection resolving model developed at ISAC-CNR (https://www.isac.cnr.it/dinamica/projects/forecasts/index.html)
SENTRY	The sentry IT platform for distributing information
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme

1. Introduction

For more than a decade, climate modeling studies have predicted an ‘invasion’ of fires in Arctic regions as a consequence of climate change (Krawchuk et al., 2009). A detailed analysis of Arctic fire regime changes and the impact on wildfire emissions indicates a large spatio-temporal variability at pan-Arctic scale (York et al., 2020; McCarty et al. 2021). The well documented increased frequency and lengthened seasonality (earlier springtime fires and fires later in autumn) of both natural and human-caused surface and ground fires (i.e. peat), all increasing total fire emissions within the Arctic (McCarty et al. 2021), leave no doubt about that the Arctic is experiencing a new fire regime. Following McCarty, here the expression fire regime means "Fire activity for a region or landscape defined by fire frequency, typical sizes of fires, annual burned area, severity, seasonality, fire type, and ignition source".

FIGURE 1 Factors influencing wildfire outcomes and management options (UNEP, 2022)

The reason for the large spatio-temporal variability of fire dynamics lies in the fact that wildfires are the result of a complex interaction of factors. Indeed, biological, meteorological, physical, and social factors all influence wildfire likelihood, behavior, duration, extent, and outcome (i.e., severity or

impact). Changes in many of these factors are increasing the risk of wildfire globally (UNEP, 2022). Figure 1 extracted from the UNEP assessment report provides an effective graphic representation of this complexity and an indication of all the factors that contribute to defining the fire regime in a particular area.

Figure 1 can be viewed along many planes, depending on the element one focuses on and the spatial and temporal scale one wishes to consider. For example, if we focus on emissions, we are looking at the problem from the point of view of the impact on the climate at a large scale. If, on the other hand, we want to focus on the impact on a more local scale, then our attention must turn to management and risk reduction actions. Since it is impossible to mitigate all risks for all fires, communities and local inhabitants have to learn to live with the residual risk of wildfire.

Figure 1 and the above remarks raise several important considerations for the scope of our service:

A - A holistic and integrated approach is required because wildfires affect a wide range of sectors and systems, such as forestry, agriculture, livestock, tourism and public health. Integrated solutions for fire management should take into account different sector policies, in order to maintain or increase the safety of people and to ensure a balance between economic growth, ecosystem services and biodiversity objectives. Human, physical and ecological elements are part of the integrated fire management approach that combines social, economic, cultural and ecological evaluations. A multi-risk approach (that is Integrated Fire Management, IFM) to address interactions with/amplifications of climatic and non-climatic drivers is also needed.

B - In developing a service for fires, it is extremely important to define the general purposes as well as the specific targets to be achieved, both in terms of products and/or users. At the same time, we must carefully evaluate:

- (i) Interactions with the respective structures in charge of risk and emergency management in various territories;
- (ii) The large amount of information and products available from several existing fire information systems (e.g. European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS), part of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service, or the Global Wildfire Information System (GWIS), a joint initiative of the GEO and the Copernicus Work Programs);
- (iii) The opportunities offered by new satellite and ground-based observation technologies.

Technology for fire monitoring and detection has greatly improved and different tools are now available that can warn us about fires in 'near-real-time' conditions. These capabilities exist at large scales, based on satellite imagery, and at local scale using cameras or drones. The latter can provide information on forest structure, composition, volume or growth and biomass amount. It can provide precise information on fire location, size and evolution, enabling effective preparation for fire suppression and the identification of evacuation areas.

The two considerations outlined above represent the starting point for the development of our INTe grated Fire Risk mAnagement (INFRA) Service. The sections that follow synthesize a process which has led us to clearly identify functions that complement existing services. In these sections, we will:

- Highlight the conceptual basis of INFRA (section 2)
- Describe the method adopted to give substance to the fundamental phase of co-design and

co-development (sections 3 and 4)

- Finally, we detail the implementation of the service, as well as a basic details of operational implementation and use (sections 5 and 6).

2. INFRA pilot service: principles and fundamental concepts

The integrated Fire Management approach links the three phases of a typical emergency management cycle:

- Prevention and preparedness;
- Detection and response;
- Restoration and adaptation (Figure 2 and EU Commission, 2018).

The challenge posed by IFM is to develop integrated solutions which take economic, environmental and social needs into account, ensuring that wildfires are managed in such a way that the safety of people and housing, economic growth and ecosystem services are maintained or bolstered. Developing more efficient and integrated solutions **requires better-informed decision-making and more cooperation and coordination**, and should be supported by evidence-based research (EU Commission 2018, pag. 21).

FIGURE 2 - The approach of integrated fire management considers each step of the management cycle and brings together the human, physical and ecological elements with an impact on the risk management process

A further challenge is to build an effective culture of fire risk management, in which the differences between the **ecological role of fire and the risk-prevention measures associated with catastrophic wildfires are clearly understood**. Society's perceptions of the risk of forest fires determines, to a large extent, people's responses in emergency situations. Forest fires are largely perceived by society as a threat. Ensuring communities' resilience to the danger of forest fires requires improvements to societal 'fire risk literacy' i.e. awareness of actual risks *and* of what constitutes an effective response in the event of an emergency. Moreover, when communicating about fire risk

and relevant prevention actions, one should never forget to stress the important ecological role that fire plays in sustaining the efficiency of various ecosystem services and economic activities (Christianson et. Al, 2022).

There is a need (i) for better integrated information on the state of risk in the present day and (ii) to contribute to the construction of an effective fire risk culture that conveys the importance of fire in keeping ecosystem services intact, and respects the knowledge and traditions of Indigenous Arctic communities, and other Arctic inhabitants. Hence, we have taken into account the following fundamental concepts when planning the development of INFRA:

1 - **FLEXIBILITY**. A wildfire service ought to be strongly related to the specific area covered (dimension and characteristics, population distribution, infrastructure, specific risks), as well as with the user and stakeholder categories it aims to serve with alerts and information for action. In designing and developing functional blocks (cfr. section 3), we have considered the need to cover a large spectrum of possible implementations, mainly at the local/regional scale.

2. - **MULTISCALE**. Complex ecological processes like wildfires, which involve many interactions between physical and biological components, are multiscale by nature. Above all we want to consider the multi-scale aspect that derives from connecting risk conditions, or the emergency conditions created by an ongoing wildfire, with the social and economic sphere. The relevance of the risk/reality of a fire event cannot be defined *a priori*. This must be considered in developing a service intended to be useful to diverse societal groups.

3. - **PROFESSIONAL as well as NON-PROFESSIONAL USERS**. The usefulness of certain information flows and service functionalities varies greatly depending on whether the intended user is a trained person who works in the fire management chain or not. At present, the information chain aimed towards non-professional subjects and communities is particularly lacking. Data systems specifically developed for wildfire monitoring usually operate on a regional (i.e. Canadian Fire Maps, EFFIS) or global scale (i.e. GWIS), offering data products rather than services. Knowing where information is held and what data is available is a substantial barrier for many to whom fire information could be of great use. In the Arctic, this obstacle is coupled with disparities in access to reliable internet connections and hardware. In developing INFRA we have considered it vital for an efficient IFM system to reach these previously overlooked, hard-to-reach groups, whilst not neglecting professional and semi-professional users.

4. - **CO-DESIGN and CO-DEVELOPMENT**. This process is fundamental for designing and implementing a fire service that is actually useful to communities and Arctic inhabitants. The next section details how we have pursued co-design and co-development within the frame of INFRA.

FIGURE 3 - INFra Service: what we like to accomplish

Use of these key concepts and methodological approaches enables us to set clear objectives and functionalities for our Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFra) Service. They are schematically shown in Figure 3 above.

If we represent IFM using the 5Rs model described by UNEP (2022), we can provide a better picture of the contribution that our INFra service would be able to provide to each of the five interlinked and often overlapping phases (Figure 4). The thickness of the arrows indicates the level of contribution that the functionalities developed in INFra should enable.

FIGURE 4 – Relative contribution of INFra to the 5 interlinked phases of an Integrated Fire Management (as identified in UNEP, 2022)

3. Co-design and Co-development

In parallel with the development of INFra, we carried out an intense process to identify interlocutors with whom to carry out co-design and co-development. The aim was to better understand the needs of different users, and to feed their insights in the design of INFra. Since Autumn 2021 we have presented the INFra pilot service at a wide range of events. This has enabled

us to meet many potential stakeholders and identify a group of key players with whom to carry out the co-design/development phase.

The General Assembly of Arctic PASSION represented a very useful opportunity to speak with communities and indigenous organizations (Sami Council, T-Wild, Gwich'in Council) to better understand their approach to the wildfire issue, their needs and current information sources. Contributing to activities of WP7 also offered us a chance to start a dialogue with municipal authorities. In the frame of a workshop organized by WP7 in June 2022, the INFRA pilot was presented as a concrete example of an activity that needs to interact with regional and local governing bodies (sub-national).

As a result of this intense dissemination activity, we now have a list of contacts covering a wide spectrum of potential stakeholders, from research institutions to Indigenous communities, forest fire managers to regional governments. Figure 5 lists the areas of the INFRA service where co-design and co-development are more important and indicates questions that co-design dialogue should help to clarify.

FIGURE 5 - Where co-design and co-development are more important

During autumn 2021 we also started a dialogue with the Northern Forum (Sakha Republic). Virtual meetings took place to exchange information. The idea at that time was to understand whether INFRA could provide support for the 2022 fire season. A meeting with the communities and important stakeholders of the Sakha Republic was planned for spring 2022. However, the Russian war against the Ukraine and the sanctions that have followed, suddenly interrupted this dialogue, forcing us to shift focus from the Sakha Republic to North America. This decision was made during Arctic Science Summit Week 2022 (ASSW2022).

The next section describes how dialogue and discussion have played a key role in developing and implementing INFRA service. To continue this effort, our strategy focuses on maintaining and strengthening dialogues with our contacts in Canada and Alaska. We plan to visit these regions to demonstrate the INFRA service and to explore concrete opportunities for communities and inhabitants to benefit from its outputs and functionalities. Implementation choices (cfr. section 5)

were made to make this process easier. The Arctic Institute of North America (AINA) in Calgary, a member of the Arctic PASSION Consortium, was able to offer support in connecting with First Nation communities of the Kluane Lake (Yukon) area. We are also carefully assessing collaborations with Gwich'in communities, considering their engagement with projects in the frame of the EPRR Arctic Council Working Group.

Considering these potential users, we have designated areas in North America to test INFRA service performance and improvements. Figure 6 presents these areas: pink numbers represent the location of Gwich'in communities (Alaska, USA). Also indicated is the Tahltan community of Dease Lake (#12, British Columbia, Canada), which is involved in the Arctic PASSION project through the Snowchange Cooperative. As described in greater depth in section 6, other areas will be included in the basic operational implementation of INFRA, in particular Fennoscandia. In Europe, it is also possible to connect INFRA with Pilot Service 5.

FIGURE 6 – The test area for INFRA in North America, including areas in Canada and Alaska

4. Lessons from stakeholders for INFRA development

Efforts to engage Indigenous representatives in the co-design and co-development of INFRA service were carried out in an informal and unstructured manner until the summer of 2023. In this section, we present a partial overview of the feedback we collected regarding needs and expectations. Our aim is to highlight the impact this exercise has had on the design and implementation of the INFRA service and its functionalities.

In spring of 2023, in cooperation with the Arctic PASSION (Pilot) Service 5 (Air pollution), we

conducted a survey to have a more robust basis for a structured analysis of the relevance of the wildfire issue for Indigenous communities and Arctic inhabitants. The survey also gathered insights on their knowledge, expectations, and the type of information/products that the service should provide. The survey was implemented on the SLIDO platform at the following link:

<https://app.sli.do/event/e5kB4Q2beKteDcT4qwMvYD>

Since its launch, we have widely distributed and made publicly available the link to collect responses from individuals engaged in the fire management system as well as non-professional/expert users.

A discussion regarding INFRA and wildfires took place with Tahltan representatives during the General Assembly of Arctic PASSION in Baveno in May 2023. Instead, dialogue with the Gwich'in representatives begun during the proposal preparation phase and has continued throughout the project duration. However, we have not yet visited the communities or the Gwich'in Council International office in Yellowknife. This delay is partly because we believe it would be more productive for a first version of the service to be operational before the first visit. It guarantees a more concrete and valuable discussion. Indeed, the flexibility and replicability of the service make it easy to develop adaptations to needs and requests emerging during a visit. At the moment, members of the Gwich'in are evaluating what has been developed so far. We plan to get their feedbacks soon, and to visit to discuss specific implementations addressing their particular needs.

The September 2023 meeting at INARI about the development of Shared Arctic Variables for wildfires allowed us to discuss with representatives of the Sámi community and of the Finnish fire management service. Later, a very important moment of discussion with the Indigenous representatives of the First Nations in Canada was the conference organized in Calgary by the Arctic Institute of North America (AINA) in February 2024. These two occasions made it possible for us to better focus on the differences between North America and European territories, that derive largely from the different emergency management systems in Europa and the Americas. In Fennoscandia there are greater structure and centralization, whereas in the Canadian and Alaskan territories the responsibilities are much more distributed/fragmented for historical reasons. Such fragmentation often makes it more challenging for Indigenous communities to feel fully involved in the management of the system. And their knowledge and experience in land management, particularly in terms of fire prevention, is often not sufficiently used or taken into account.

Our main contact with municipalities and local government entities was the secretariat of the Arctic Mayor's Forum (AMF). With them, we are proposing to promote and organize a webinar to present the INFRA service specifically to municipal representatives.

The interaction with other research institutions and other projects has been explored especially during 2024 as another way to try to better approach and connect with local realities. With such aim, we interfaced with the Arctic Institute of North America (AINA), and we have plans to open an information point on INFRA at the Kluana Lake station in Yukon. A similar approach could also be followed in other stations and/or in some communities/organizations that make themselves available. Indeed, we understood that awareness about the usefulness and value of a service must be born and grow from the user's side and cannot be imposed and conveyed from above. This approach obviously requires time to prepare the right informational material and possibly train those who can then locally answer the enquiries of potential users.

Additionally, we recently began interacting with the US RNA CoObs project at UAF, Fairbanks,

Alaska. We expect this collaboration to highlight the societal value of the INFRA service. We seek to align INFRA with other initiatives in Alaska and Canada with the aim to increase the responsiveness and resilience of Indigenous communities to wildfire challenges (e.g. The Fire Adapted Communities Learning Network – <https://fireadapted.org/>).

In early stages of the project (end of 2021 and beginning of 2022) and thanks to the support of Snowchange we engaged with the President of the Northern Forum Academy. Although these contacts were interrupted as a consequence of Russia's war, the insights gained were valuable. The concerns raised by Siberian Indigenous communities in a region such as Sacha-Yakutia closely mirrored those identified by communities in North America and Fennoscandia. Here, the centralization of the emergency management system exacerbates the problem of the physical and institutional distance from the local realities. It creates barriers to effective dialogue and participation, not much different from those faced by the populations of North America, where the competences are divided between many levels and agencies.

Two key aspects require significant attention in the further development of the INFRA service to effectively serve a large variety of users:

(i) at the level of end users, communities and municipalities, there is limited awareness on the wealth of information and services already available at international and national levels. Furthermore, the ability to utilize these tools is limited because of their relative complexity as they are typically designed for expert users.

(ii) many stakeholders, in particular Indigenous communities, highlight a lack of involvement in the Integrated Fire Management process. They express concern that Indigenous knowledge, approaches and best practices in land and vegetation management are poorly used during the risk reduction phases (cfr. Figure 4). Moreover, their direct involvement in the readiness and response phases occurs only very close to the emergency, when the situation has already escalated into a critical one. Combined with limited human and technical resources of Indigenous communities and municipalities, it has a strong impact on the level of preparedness for emergencies, including wildfires.

These two challenges are closely interconnected. Access to comprehensive information not only raises the level of readiness but also enables quicker response to emergencies at individual, family, community and municipality levels. Addressing these challenges should be a priority for INFRA and its services. We expect to give concrete answers by creating tools that are able to improve the situation and bridge these divides. In relation to the first aspect - access to information - we have carefully designed INFRA to accommodate varying levels of user expertise. The goal is to effectively serve both non-expert individuals, and communities/municipalities that may possess resources and skills to receive more complex information. The implementation in a cloud computing environment and with a multilevel approach appeared to be an appropriate solution for this purpose:

- The basic level (see end of section 5.3, pag. 27 for more details) provides a quantity of information and functionality that can be quickly learned and used by a non-expert user. It will be supported by informative and descriptive material – an ongoing effort which will keep us busy until the end of the project and beyond.
- The more advanced level (realized by now in the test mode) is designed for more specialized

users. It generates tailored messages to different categories of experts. It will include an option of dissemination of messages which is intended only for those who have responsibilities at the local level of governance and management.

The advanced level should help local communities and municipalities to interact with the services that are responsible for managing the territory and emergencies. Use of INFRA at this level provides local government entities with a direct channel of access to the information available at a national and international level. The interface allows to get an access to current situation and its evolution and to plan the dissemination of tailored information messages. In line with their responsibilities, these entities can approach the emergency/fire management services to jointly decide on appropriate actions. This fosters a virtuous circle in which every involved party actively works to keep a high level of situation awareness both for local government bodies and for individual inhabitants.

The proximity to the territories and the local realities adds the option of adapting choices and actions to specific conditions. Giving Indigenous communities and municipalities the opportunity to analyze the situation and to operate before the emergency reaches critical levels, INFRA facilitates the integration of Indigenous knowledge on the territory and its management into the integrated Fire management system. Such integration significantly improves the overall resilience of Arctic communities in facing wildfires. Figure 7 provides schematic representation of this process, illustrating how it can be realized in the INFRA scheme and architecture.

FIGURE 7 – A schematic of how INFRA could help to overcome the barriers bringing the formulation of tailored information more near to the final user.

The Arctic PASSION (Pilot) Service 1 (‘Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge’; <https://nextcloud.awi.de/s/Q75nf3ocsdFRgE>) is a valuable resource for integration of Indigenous knowledge into databases about the fire regimes and changes they are causing. There exists a large body of Indigenous knowledge and observations devoted to fires and changing fire regimes. For example, the Gwich’in database collection, contributed through Pilot Service 1, includes reports on the environmental causes driving fire regime changes, such as warmer temperatures, especially in winter and summer, and increased variability in weather patterns. These observations also highlight the impact of more frequent forest fires, including permafrost degradation and ground slumping.

On the basis of the concept illustrated in Figure 7, one of the objectives for INFRA will be to explore ways to make the Indigenous knowledge contained in the Pilot Service 1 databases more accessible to those responsible for crafting tailored messages for diverse user groups. This knowledge package includes information on the traditional land management, environmental conditions that can favor fires, and understanding of factors causing changes in fire regime.

5. Development and implementation of INFRA

This section details the concrete implementation of the concepts described in section 2. The choices we have made are aimed at making the service as useful and usable as possible by semi- or non-professional users, as we have increasingly understood that it is on this front that there is the greatest need. INFRA makes use of specific IT platforms. All those currently used to realize the INFRA service were developed for a different, broader scope, even if always connected with risk management. Section 5.2. details what has been specifically developed for use in INFRA.

5.1. Information layers

The variables and parameters currently represented in INFRA have been selected primarily with the aim of providing a clear picture of a fire situation that does not overload users who wish to directly access the web-based GIS platform which supports the information phase of the service (see paragraph 5.4.1). This need for accessibility is balanced with facilitating the proper functioning of the professional ‘control room’ and covering all the informational categories that an information service dedicated to fires must cover (Figure 8). The experts called upon to integrate fire-related information and then disseminate it to users can decide to use INFRA in synergy with other services, thus accessing additional information and products that they deem useful.

As shown in figure 8, the information categories to be covered include:

- (i) The evaluation of vegetation fire risk (risk indices);
- (ii) The probability of ignition events of natural origin, e.g. lightning;
- (iii) Weather conditions;
- (iv) Active fires and the damage they have caused.

FIGURE 8 – Information categories in INFRA

To draw attention to local situations, INFRA has introduced a 'sites of interest' category, so that the control room can more easily focus on these sites and easily extract information to pass on to targeted users. Information layers include:

- (i) Selected risk indexes, arising from external services or evaluated by INFRA at high resolution (0.5 km);
- (ii) Information about natural risk of ignition (lightning, convective activity) at medium (8 km) and high (1 km) resolution;
- (iii) Information on active fires and burned areas;
- (iv) Information on weather conditions;
- (v) Ancillary information such as fuel maps, land cover, protected areas;
- (vi) Indication of point of interest.

Concerning the products and information layers contained in INFRA, it is important to consider:

1 - Plentiful information about fires can be found by accessing various existing services, both global (GWIS) and regional / national (EFFIS, the Canadian Wildland Fire Information System, the Alaska Wildland Fire Information Map Series, or the Alaska Interagency Coordination Center Dashboards). Currently INFRA contains some information from those sources. For a later concrete application, more information layers can be included in INFRA for routine operations. In special cases, a control room with good data connection and sufficient expertise could also decide to use other services in synergy with INFRA

2 - With reference to the co-design and co-development process described above, we indicated that user needs and technological capacities should help define the development of INFRA and the information it focuses on gathering and conveying (see Figure 5). Going forward, this dialogue with key stakeholders will help tailor the service further. The characteristics of the AEGIS platform make these modifications and additions easy.

3 – Currently 12-13 weather fields have been selected for inclusion in INFRA, based on the usefulness of these variables in representing the weather conditions that impact on fires and their management. Thus, they support the work of experts in a control room and the management of live fire events. Many more fields are routinely saved (60 fields in total). In particular, the predicted temperature and humidity conditions of the soil are stored at 13 levels up to 22 meters deep. An index like FWI (Lawson and Armitage, 2008) actually uses quite basic weather information, partly due to the fact that the original development of this index dates back to the 1960s. The meteorological suite used by INFRA, and in particular its complex parameterization of surface and soil processes, offers development opportunities. To our knowledge, only the Finnish service dedicates similar attention to the management and forecasting of weather fields. We view these weather variables as essential for making accurate assessments of the state of vegetation with respect to fire risk.

5.2. The INFRA pilot service

Figure 9 shows the INFRA pilot service scheme that we have implemented, starting from the principles and purposes described in section 2 and making use of instruments and tools

suitably modified and adapted to the specific needs of INFRA.

Figure 9 – Structure of the INFRA pilot service INFRA. Also presented is the data flow from external sources and between components.

The two main elements of INFRA are the platforms used to implement and manage two macro-functions:

- 1 - The collection, integration and transformation of information collected from the ground, as well as the products created by INFRA (INFRA-AEGIS);
- 2 - The dissemination of information through messages and other outputs calibrated to the needs and capabilities of the users INFRA aims to serve (INFRA-SENTRY).

These two platforms and the changes made to the initial tools (AEGIS and SENTRY) to make them fully functional for the purposes of INFRA are illustrated in the following two subsections.

For the sake of clarity, the INFRA-FIDESYS platform is not shown in the diagram in Figure 9. This oversees a third macro-function of INFRA, namely the collection of information and observations for the identification of fire events through the combined use of human and/or automatic ground and satellite systems. The close dependence of this part of INFRA on the specific conditions to which it is addressed has meant that, for now, this functionality has not actually been included in the implementation, but has only been developed externally. The hope is that as part of the continuation of the INFRA Project it can be implemented in specific cases, supplying information from ground observations. In the absence of such observations satellite data collected from other services, such as GWIS, can be used to fill the gap.

The rectangle with red hatching found in Figure 9 indicates the part of the system that is supported by Cloud architecture (see section 5.3).

With the control room box we indicate a 'place' in which experts can sit and make use of INFRA functionalities, providing support and information to professional, semi-professional or non-professional users. Considering the Cloud architecture adopted, such a control room can be located where it is most convenient/useful. The control room does not require huge

hardware and/or large computational capability. A fast and stable internet connection is one necessity for such a control room. Another is the capability to display information continuously on a screen. We will look at the needs and characteristics of a control room in section 4.3, where the topic of how to operate INFRA is discussed.

5.2.1. INFRA-AEGIS

Thanks to this platform all the information layers produced by INFRA or collected from many other sources and services can be presented, combined and integrated. In this way, INFRA-AEGIS can support fire event management as well as engage and support users. Several modifications were made to the original AEGIS IT platforms to integrate inputs/data, support event management, distribute info, engage and support users.

Connection to the GWIS service, in order to collate all the parameters deemed useful, has been implemented. Every time you select a parameter provided by this service, the platform directly collects this data from the GWIS FTP site (for our area of interest). Since we are operating in a cloud environment and can locate the control room to have an excellent internet connection and no risk of connection interruption, this approach offers guarantees not dissimilar to those of a service that stores information locally in terms of Integrated Fire Management (IFM).

INFRA-AEGIS offers those who work for fire management two advantages: (1) they can focus automatically on a predefined area of interest, making it easier carry out integration and analysis of the situation, and (2) they have instruments to select and store images and maps in a format suitable for inclusion in alert messages or in action communications. The ability of INFRA-SENTRY (cfr. below) to disseminate alert messages/action communications through many channels means INFRA can serve areas lacking quick internet. INFRA can even, to some extent, serve areas lacking cell phone coverage.

For non-professional users who wish to independently connect to INFRA-AEGIS to understand and follow a fire situation and its evolution, the need/limitation of having a continuously good internet connection remains. But in this sense INFRA is no different or worse than other services such as GWIS and the Canadian and Alaska national services.

With respect to end-user benefit the **points of interest** highlighted in INFRA are of great importance and enable the service to emphasize the local dimensions of fire risk. At the moment the size of each point of interest is 50x50 km. Based on user needs, this could certainly be defined differently. However, it is laborious to more freely allow users (primarily those in the control room) to decide the value of this area from time to time. If an area is selected as a point of interest, the system can zoom in only on this area. The point of interest option, presented in Figure 10, is very important from an INFRA-SENTRY perspective.

Figure 10 – On the left FWI and active fires (green dots) over the test area for INFRA in North America on July 5, 2023. The square with orange borders is centered on the Tetlit Zheh (aka Fort McPherson) community. On the right is the automatic zoom performed by INFRA-AEGIS on this 50x50 km area. As can be seen, this zoom allows us to highlight that an active fire is located at a distance of approximately 30-40 km from Fort McPherson. (left bottom of the zoom). Tools available in INFRA-AEGIS for calculating distances and areas allow the distance to the fire front to be accurately assessed to be 39.5 km.

It is very useful to present information related to active fires and/or burned areas, and information related to damage assessment, over a period of time rather than a specific day, and to visualize this time period in sequence to give a clear view of the fire event's evolution. This can help experts in the control room to correctly interpret information and prepare alert messages, as well as messages for fire management actions. To this end, users can select any period of time that is of interest and visualize it as a video or a frame by frame.

5.2.2. INFRA-SENTRY

The question of how to provide information in an understandable and suitable way to a wider community of users is the challenge that every emergency management service/system must deal with. It's a problem to which many of the fire services that have been developed for general use across the web have paid far too little attention. In developing a response to this challenge, it is useful to refer to a field such as meteorology where good solutions have been developed. The comparison with meteorology can be particularly useful especially if, as is the case with INFRA, you want to try to reach and inform the inhabitants of a certain area/region in an adequate/widespread way and not just the institutional level of those in charge of managing a territory and/or emergency.

Meteorological models can supply grids of dozens if not hundreds of weather

parameters at different levels in the atmosphere. The most sophisticated graphic elaborations can highlight aspects of atmospheric circulation and conditions, but an expert eye is needed to be able to read these graphs and imagine them in terms of meteorological phenomena such as we are used to and interested in. Thus the problem weather forecasters are faced with is conceptually the same as that facing us with regards to wildfires: how to place the information in a language (textual or graphic) that is understandable to as wide a range of individuals as possible.

There are two lessons from meteorological practice which we must keep in mind:

(a) It is important to try to make it a public habit to find out about a fire situation and its evolution. In the field of meteorology fostering this kind of public engagement and forethought is simpler because we all have experience of what happens when we don't anticipate it will rain and we go out without an umbrella. But this does not exempt us from trying to educate the public in the case of fires, with the aim of making everyone more aware and reducing the risk that they will take potentially dangerous actions;

(b) Try to avoid diluting the information content so that those more prepared and able to appreciate a greater information content tune out. This is particularly important for semi-professionals involved in the Integrated Fire Management system (e.g. Indigenous Fire Managers).

Meteorologists have sought to overcome these challenges by creating multiple levels of re-elaboration through which different audiences can access and understand weather information. Television weather channels represent the most important intermediate level of widespread information transfer from weather services to individual citizens, taking the local scale into account. They also aspire to play an educational role. Like all operations that are also commercial, they have limits and flaws. In particular, they tend to convey too much information at a very basic level and are time consuming. The websites of the various weather services tend to fall into the trap of passing on a lot of information but leaving the burden of understanding/interpreting/integrating it at the spatial scale that interests the user.

Starting from the above knowledge base, that is the civil protection experience of CAE used in developing the SENTRY platform, the specific needs and differences existing between the meteorological issue and that of wildfires, and finally the peculiarities of users and communication systems in the Arctic, we have developed the INFRA-SENTRY dissemination module in such a way as to:

- Give the high level of expertise in the control room maximum flexibility in data integration and generation of messages with differentiated levels of information for different categories of user;
- Prioritize the local scale over the regional one;
- Aggregate the maximum possible amount of information in graphic/map format, for inclusion in the messages;
- Allow the activation of intermediate levels to be defined from time to time, and fully involve Indigenous, other local communities and the professional and semi-

professional expertise present;

- Reduce to a minimum the problems deriving from communication limitations (especially the internet) by using a plurality of channels and sensitively sizing the message load in terms of bytes;
- Encode messages according to the CAP standard (cfr. Below) so that they can, if necessary, be disseminated to the various levels of the chain that manages fires in an integrated manner.

While INFRA-AEGIS, in similarity with services such as GWIS, Canadian Wildland fire Integrated system (CWFIS), and others, can be made freely accessible if desired (for now it is password protected), INFRA-SENTRY will always and only be available to those who have the authority and responsibility for generating and transferring information or alert messages.

The community level is certainly an excellent level to try to operate a transfer of information aimed at the needs of the individual user. In fact, considering the extent of the territory and the distance between one community and another, circumscribing the information in terms of geographical area can serve a dual purpose of making the work of a semi-professional easier, increasing his/her/their attention, and at the same time reducing the problem connected to unreliable and expensive digital communication infrastructures (internet).

An important aspect to consider in developing communication with users is that of standardization. INFRA will adopt the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP), a standard developed about 10 years ago under the coordination of the OASIS OPEN non-profit organization. CAP has a simple, generalized format for exchanging all hazard emergency alerts and public warnings across different networks. CAP allows a consistent warning message to be disseminated simultaneously over many different warning systems, thus increasing warning effectiveness while simplifying the warning task. CAP also facilitates the detection of emerging patterns in local warnings of various kinds, which might indicate an undetected hazard or hostile act. CAP provides a template for effective warning messages based on best practices identified in academic research and from real-world experience.

Operators entering information and messages in INFRA-SENTRY will have at their disposal a mask (Figure 11) through which to select users they aim to reach, prepare a message in free text, and add maps and other graphical information with a minimum load in terms of bytes.

Figure 11 – The mask for operators to generate messages/alert

The system will translate the message in CAP standard and will use the CAP format to activate all communication instruments identified for the distribution group. Figure 12 provides a schema of how information disseminated through INFRA-SENTRY can move from the control room to users.

Figure 12 – How INFRA-SENTRY will work to disseminate messages/alerts

5.3 Operating INFRA through the Cloud

Ease of access and standard information technologies are a fundamental requirement to make the system available to people, worldwide. A computer, a smartphone and an internet browser are often the only thing available to users and therefore must be all that is needed for the service to be successful.

For that reason, we have chosen to utilize Cloud architecture, which is easy to implement and manage.

The architecture consists of three virtual machines configured as follows (Figure 13):

1. **Web Services:** a virtual internet-based machine that contains exclusively Nginx software. It is open-source software that acts as a reverse proxy and manages all security features. It creates a level of logical separation between the public network and internal services, which are therefore not directly accessible from the internet. It also manages the termination of TLS/SSL tunnels used for encryption in the https protocol. Thanks to this component, it is possible to set security rules to guarantee greater reliability in the system. In case of very numerous accesses, Nginx can also be configured to balance incoming traffic on more than one server, ensuring scalability.

2. **Core Services:** this virtual machine contains all the services described in the project: Aegis, Sentry and FideSys. Moreover, there are some ancillary services that guarantee functionality necessary for the main services:

A GeoServer is an open-source server written in Java that allows users to share, process and edit geospatial data. Designed for interoperability, it publishes data from any major spatial data source using open standards. GeoServer has evolved to become an easy method of connecting existing information to virtual globes such as Google Earth and NASA World Wind as well as to web-based maps such as OpenLayers, Leaflet, Google Maps and Bing Maps. GeoServer functions as the reference implementation of the Open Geospatial Consortium Web Feature Service standard, and also implements the Web Map Service, Web Coverage Service and Web Processing Service specifications.

B Datalife is the software that manages all the system configuration and data consistency within the SQL database. In the case of monitoring stations located throughout the area, it also manages data acquisition.

C Datascape is a web service that exposes the data present in Datalife/SQL. It implements an OPENAPI 3 compatible Rest API service and ensures communication between Aegis, Sentry, FideSys and SQL modules.

3 **Database Services:** this virtual machine contains the SQL engine, a relational database for storing all system data and configurations.

All the architecture described above is hosted within an AWS Cloud platform in the Milan data center. The sizing of these machines is dynamic, due to the nature of the Cloud. It is therefore possible to decrease or increase the physical characteristics of the system according to access and performance needs: number of CPUs, disk space, network traffic, etc. This ensures that the system can be scaled very reactively based on actual usage, saving resources when not in use.

Figure 13 – The schematic of INFRA architecture in the cloud environment

Access to INFRA-AEGIS and INFRA-SENTRY platforms is regulated at the moment through a password. In Figure 14 is presented the front page for INFRA-AEGIS.

Figure 14 – The access page to INFRA-AEGIS

The Cloud environment and architecture based on virtual machines makes it very easy to realize different versions and make INFRA versions with different functionalities available. It is very useful to be able to make a potentially operational service available while we continue to develop more products and functionalities and test them across selected time periods. This opportunity is mainly useful for INFRA-AEGIS.

At present we have implemented two versions for the area of interest in North America:

1 – A stable account with layers produced externally. In practice, this account could be made operational now if a sort of control room is organized. In this version the selected area could easily be extended according to user needs.

2 – A test-and-develop account, where the products and information layers that INFRA is developing - primarily meteorological layers- are gradually tested, until the list shown in table 1 is completed (see section 5.1) . In this case, the system is not able to run in operational mode (since the available resources do not allow the BOLAM and MOLOCH forecast chain to run in operational mode) but can carry out tests on the two selected areas for the two periods of 3 months during which the weather fields were acquired and stored.

We have not yet created a potentially operational account for the selected area in the Sakha Region (Yakutia) for obvious geo-political reasons. This is a real shame considering the great interest shown at the beginning of the project by the stakeholders and the strong ties existing between them and some members of the Arctic PASSION Consortium.

6. Operational implementation of INFRA using core platforms

With the aim of highlighting the potential of INFRA and better clarifying how it can be useful to a large audience of potential users, in this section we describe how basic functionalities of INFRA can be used to create an operational service. See figure 9 (section 5.2) for a graphic depiction of the service and its data flow.

Our ability to directly involve relatively small actors, such as administrations or organizations in small Arctic communities or municipalities in this work derives from the limited resources necessary to set up the service:

- (a) The availability of 2-3 people, not necessarily full-time fire and rescue professionals;
- (b) A location from which they can access the internet with good speed;
- (c) Monitors to report the information that INFRA-AEGIS provides and/or INFRA-SENTRY screens, and a computer (basic) is all that is necessary.

Routine operations would be described schematically through the following steps:

STEP 1

Operators, i.e. people able to give time to the service with modalities determined by those who want to set up and use it, are able to access the INFRA-AEGIS platform.

STEP2

Using INFRA-AEGIS functionalities, Operators can acquire information on the current fire situation and its evolution, risk status etc. These people can, for example, compare the probability of ignition with the risk state of the vegetation, monitor the distribution and distance of active fires, evaluate fire evolution using the continuous visualization functions for a chosen period of days, and calculate distances and areas. These people can focus on points of interest (areas currently defined as 50 x 50 km in size) and save maps in 'png' format, showing the content produced locally on the computer.

STEP3

Once Operators have a clear idea of the situation, they are able to connect to the INFRA-SENTRY

platform and translate what they have assessed into text messages. Their messages may include some or all of the png files previously produced. These images support and clarify the text.

Communication towards users can be standardized and made very robust by preparing models and templates for these messages, which can be recalled and used to produce the information to be distributed.

The time necessary to follow STEPS 1-3 is not huge. This means it is not necessary to have people dedicated to the service at all times. Time investment can be modulated according to the needs and state of the emergency. The overall approach is similar to a weather forecast approach. We believe that, in the long-term it could produce a positive effect in terms of public awareness with respect to wildfires.

INFRA Cloud implementations can be easily duplicated and adapted to the specific needs of many different users, in terms of area of interest, information layers etc.

The distribution chain is established from the start by identifying the contacts and/or groups to be reached, as well as the technical methods by which they will be reached (text messages, phone calls, e-mail, social media). The different contacts and groups can be assigned or assume tasks and roles in the system and therefore be reached by very specific messages that refer to their role and task. A specific characteristic of INFRA is that it delivers information to a more local and less centralized level, making its adaptation and adjustment to local requirements easy: messages are attuned to the needs of local users, making use of the most suitable language/format.

To adapt service for a specific user, the only necessary steps are:

- 1 - To collectively identify the area of interest;
- 2 - To collect - via the form provided in Appendix I - information on target people to reach with messages and information;
- 3 - To define a template/format for messages and agree on a language to use and any information that you won't distribute. Information content can be tailored for each different user category;
- 4 - Identify/secure experts who will act as the key operators for Steps 1-3;
- 5 – Set up working space and resources for the Operators' to work.

As long as the project is active, the presence of INFRA and its versions, stored on the Cloud, will be supported by the project partners CNR and CAE. We also are looking for people in Italy who could play the role of Operators, as described above, so that we are able to develop concrete proposals to activate the service with interested users in 2024.

7. Conclusion and next steps

This report has described the design and development of the pilot service for INFRA fires, from the definition of principles to concrete implementation. The main objective of INFRA is to provide tools and services that give communities, municipalities and individual citizens greater access to information on the current status and impact of large-scale fires, in accordance with their interest and needs. It is the users who define and decide the levels of information which each specific implementation of INFRA will provide, alongside existing official services and channels. INFRA can complement services at national and/or regional scale by offering greater flexibility in terms of

spatial scale, the profile and methods of dissemination, and the format of the information itself. INFRA can increase the agency and awareness of users who currently lie outside official lines of emergency management when it comes to wildfires. At the current stage of development the main features have been designed, though not all have been completed. This will be done during the second part of Arctic PASSION, in close interaction with users.

The next steps involve the completion of the development and advanced testing of INFRA functions. We will also promote the service with the aim of (i) increasing the degree of co-design and co-development, and (ii) identifying Arctic communities and/or municipalities that could help us to test operational implementation, illustrated in section 9, in the fire seasons of 2024 and 2025.

More complex and demanding implementations are possible. They could be realized by adding and combining the other modules that we have described in the previous sections. Due to the limited resources of the project and the objective of developing a pilot, the potential that INFRA can offer using these additional modules will be investigated in test mode, considering two years, 2021 and 2022, and the three summer months (June-August). Specific INFRA installations on the Cloud have been made and are/will be used to fully develop, test and optimize all envisaged functionalities.

As a final step, we also are working to connect the pilot service on wildfires with the pilot service on air quality.

This report is meant to document the current status of the initiative and describe INFRA's basic functionality. Increasing the relevance and quality of service to potential users requires further co-creation. To achieve this, we will soon conduct specific surveys/interviews which aim to:

- Assess relevance of the different information layers for different users and user categories and identify the need for more layers (i.e. about fire effects on air quality at low spatial scale);
- Collect supplementary information from users/communities (i.e. critical/relevant infrastructures, ground-based early detection systems);
- Assess wildfire management organization at community/local/regional level;
- Assess relevance/value of fire effects and damages;
- Identify communities and/or other users for service testing;
- Adapt and develop INFRA functionalities and products accordingly.

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Appendix I-

Information from users for INFRA-SENTRY

Module to collect information on users of INFRA service

Contacts

For each contact please provide following information:

1 - Name

2 - Surname

3 - Role with respect wildfire management

(general description. Please specify if more engage in prevention, event management, post-event actions)

4 - How to reach him :

e-mail: (from HH:MM to HH:MM during the day)
(days of the week)

cell phone (sms): (from HH:MM to HH:MM during the day)
(days of the week)

cell phone (Phone call) (from HH:MM to HH:MM during the day)
(days of the week)

telegram profile (from HH:MM to HH:MM during the day)
(days of the week)

PLEASE ADD OTHERS MODALITIES IF EXIST FOR THIS CONTACT

Groups

Contacts can be, if considered useful, grouped (e.g. an entire intervention team, the crew of a rescue vehicle, etc.). If you like, a contact can be included in many groups. Non limits or restrictions. For each Group, please provide the following information

1 - Group Name:

2 - List of group Members (sufficient Name Surname)

3 - Group Leader

4 - Role of the Group in the organization and wildfire management

NOTE - Groups are not necessary to operate INFRA. So answer to this point only if is really useful for you.

Distribution Lists

These lists will determine the modalities with which the information, messages, alarms

arising from INFRA will reach you. Defining them in the right way you can allow INFRA to SEND the RIGHT INFORMATION to the RIGHT PERSON/GROUP with the RIGHT COMMUNICATION CHANNEL

When experts in the control room will operate they can prepare different messages for the different distribution lists. For example, if you like to reach both professional with large amount of information, and other generic users with just a simple update on the status, you can create two different distribution lists. The distribution list name can then be used to provide some indication to the control room operator to avoid mistakes.

For each Distribution lists COMMUNICATION CHANNELS (sms, e-mail, phone call, social media, ...) will be defined. The software will check for each contact included in the list if he indicated or not this modality. Only contacts with at disposal this channel will be served.

The information about the period of the day and day of the week in which the channel is active, will able INFRA to avoid any unwanted contact

For each Distribution list you like to create, please provide the following information

1 - Distribution list Name (max 250 char)

please try to use the name to give some indication about the scope and role of the list and type of information usually expected by them (e.g. fire manager, intervention team, generic user, etc.)

2 - Contacts to include in the distribution list (sufficient Name Surname)

if you have created groups you can indicate them and add residual contacts

3 - Communication channel to use:

e-mail	YES/NO	
sms	YES/NO	
phone call	YES/NO	
telegram	YES/NO	
OTHERS	YES/NO	specify:

